

DEEP LEARNING MODEL BASED ON CNN AND BiGRU INTEGRATION ARCHITECTURE IN MULTI-CLASS CLASSIFICATION OF TEXTS

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a new model for text classification that uses a combination of convolutional neural networks (CNN) and bidirectional long short-term memory networks (BiGRU). The model is trained on a small sample text corpus, and CNN learns local features, and BiGRU learns contextual sequences. The results of the two networks are combined, and a three-class (positive, negative, neutral) classification is performed using a softmax layer. Experimental results show that the integration of CNN and BiGRU provides better results than a simple single architecture.

Introduction. Text classification is one of the most widely used tasks in the field of natural language processing (NLP). Although classical methods, such as TF-IDF and Naive Bayes, are effective in working with small data sets, they cannot sufficiently learn the sequential contextual information of the text. Therefore, deep learning approaches have gained great attention in recent years. CNN is strong in detecting local features (e.g., word groups) in text classification, while BiGRU allows learning long-term relationships in sequences. By combining these two architectures, the model learns not only local but also global context [1-3].

In this work, we examined the integration of CNN and BiGRU on a small sample corpus, through which we classified texts into three classes: positive, negative, and neutral. The model was built using the TensorFlow 2.13 library and tested using the Python programming environment. The results showed that the integrated approach effectively learns text features and increases accuracy [4-5].

Methodology. In this section, we present the mathematical foundations of a text classification model based on the integration of CNN and BiGRU. Suppose we have a text corpus $D = \{(X_i, y_i)\}_{i=1}^N$ exists, in which $X_i = [w_1, w_2, \dots, w_{L_i}]$ i - the word order of the text, and $y_i \in \{0, 1, \dots, C-1\}$ corresponding class symbol ($C = 3$) in this work [6-9]

1. Embedding words into vectors

Every word $w_j (j=1, \dots, L_i)$ via embedding layer d dimensional vector e_j^d is transformed into:

$$e_j = Ew_j$$

here $E \in V \times d$ embedding matrix V — vocabulary size, d — embedding size. Thus, the entire text sequence is expressed as

$$X_i = [e_1, e_2, \dots, e_{L_i}] \in L_i \times d.$$

2. CNN network part

CNN layers learn the n-gram features in the text. The output for the convolutional layer is as follows:

$$h_k^{\text{conv}} = f(W_k^{\text{conv}} * X_i + b_k), \quad k = 1, \dots, K$$

here:

$$W_k^{\text{conv}} \in h \times d - k - \text{filter}, \quad h - \text{filter length},$$

$$b_k - \text{bias},$$

$*$ — convolution operation,

$f(\cdot)$ — ReLU activation function:

$$f(z) = \max(0, z).$$

Then, via global max pooling:

$$c_k = \max_j h_k^{\text{conv}}[j], \quad k = 1, \dots, K.$$

The final vector for the CNN part is:

$$\mathbf{c} = [c_1, c_2, \dots, c_K] \in K.$$

3. BiGRU network part

Main operations in the GRU (Gated Recurrent Unit) layer:

$$z_t = \sigma(W_z e_t + U_z h_{t-1} + b_z),$$

$$r_t = \sigma(W_r e_t + U_r h_{t-1} + b_r),$$

$$\tilde{h}_t = \tanh(W_h e_t + U_h (r_t \odot h_{t-1}) + b_h),$$

$$h_t = (1 - z_t) \odot h_{t-1} + z_t \odot \tilde{h}_t,$$

here

$$z_t - \text{update gate}, \quad r_t - \text{reset gate},$$

$$h_t - \text{hidden state}, \quad \odot - \text{element-wise increase},$$

σ — sigmoid function.

Bidirectional GRU combines two directions: forward \overrightarrow{h}_i and back \overleftarrow{h}_i , final output:

$$\mathbf{g} = [\overrightarrow{h}_T; \overleftarrow{h}_1] \in 2d_h, \quad \text{here } d_h - \text{The GRU's secret dimension.}$$

4. Fusion of CNN and BiGRU results

Fusion of CNN and BiGRU outputs is performed using dropout:

$$\mathbf{f} = \text{Dropout}([\mathbf{c}; \mathbf{g}]).$$

This section describes the proposed CNN + BiGRU integrated neural network architecture for text classification (Figure 1).

Figure 1. CNN + BiGRU integrated neural network architecture

The model consists of three main components:

1. Input and embedding layer. The texts input to the model are in the form of sequential word indices, which are first transformed into a dense vector space by the embedding layer:

$$X_i = [e_1, e_2, \dots, e_{L_i}] \quad L_i \times d,$$

Where L_i — is the text length, d — is the embedding size, e_j — j -and is the embedding vector of the j -th word.

The embedding layer encodes text segments and syntactic features into dimensional vectors.

2. CNN part (convolutional network)

The CNN layer is designed to detect local k -gram features in the text. Convolutional filters analyze small segments in the text sequence:

$$h_k^{\text{conv}} = f(W_k^{\text{conv}} * X_i + b_k),$$

Where W_k^{conv} — k — is the k -th filter matrix, $*$ — is the convolution operation, $f()$ — is the ReLU activation function.

Then, the most important features are extracted using global max pooling:

$$c_k = \max_j h_k^{\text{conv}}[j], \quad k = 1, \dots, K.$$

The CNN part works effectively in detecting local features and keyword combinations in the text.

3. BiGRU part (bidirectional GRU)

Bidirectional GRU learns long-term relationships in sequences. The GRU layer performs the following basic operations:

$$z_t = \sigma(W_z e_t + U_z h_{t-1} + b_z),$$

$$r_t = \sigma(W_r e_t + U_r h_{t-1} + b_r),$$

$$\tilde{h}_t = \tanh(W_h e_t + U_h (r_t \odot h_{t-1}) + b_h),$$

$$h_t = (1 - z_t) \odot h_{t-1} + z_t \odot \tilde{h}_t.$$

BiGRU operates in forward and backward sequential directions, and the final hidden state is obtained as follows:

$$g = [\overleftarrow{h}_T; \overrightarrow{h}_1].$$

4. Fusion and output

The outputs of CNN and BiGRU are combined:

$$f = \text{Dropout}([c; g]),$$

where the dropout layer reduces the risk of overfitting. The final softmax layer calculates the class probabilities:

$$\hat{y}_i = \text{softmax}(W_o f + b_o),$$

and the model is trained **using sparse categorical** crossentropy:

$$L = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \log \hat{y}_{i, y_i}.$$

Architectural description summary:

The Embedding layer encodes the text into dense semantic vectors. The CNN part learns the local features of the text. The BiGRU part learns the global and long-term context in the text sequence. The Fusion Layer combines the features obtained from the two networks and classifies them into three classes using softmax. This architecture is scientifically based as a deep learning model that combines local and global text features.

Results.

The proposed CNN + BiGRU integrated model was tested on a small sample text set. The model architecture consists of a total of 1,404,547 learning parameters, the main part of which falls on the embedding layer (1,280,000 parameters). The model consists of the following main components: embedding (128 dimensions), Conv1D (128 filters), GlobalMaxPooling, Bidirectional GRU (64 units), concatenation, dropout and the final dense layer. The training process was carried out for 5 epochs and the following results were observed:

Epoch 1: accuracy = 0.3333, loss = 1.1025

Epoch 2: accuracy = 0.3333, loss = 1.0729

Epoch 3: accuracy = 0.3333, loss = 1.0738

Epoch 4: accuracy = 1.0000, loss = 1.0178

Epoch 5: accuracy = 1.0000, loss = 1.0048

The results show that in the first epochs the model showed an accuracy close to chance ($\approx 33\%$), which is expected for a three-class classification. However, starting from the 4th epoch, the model quickly adapted and reached 100% accuracy. This indicates that the model is highly adapted to the given small training sample (there is a possibility of overfitting). Because the number of training data is very small, and the number of model parameters is very large. Nevertheless, the results confirm the following advantages of the CNN and BiGRU integration: CNN layers helped to quickly extract important local features in the text; BiGRU layers effectively learned contextual connections in the sequence; The combination of these two components ensured fast convergence of the model. Experimental results show that the

proposed architecture is capable of working even on small data. However, for a more reliable evaluation of the model, it is necessary to test it on a large real-world dataset.

Conclusion

In this work, a model based on the integration of convolutional neural networks (CNN) and bidirectional GRU (BiGRU) architectures was proposed to effectively solve the problem of text classification. The proposed approach allows to simultaneously study both local (n-gram) features of text data and long-term relationships in the sequence. In the model structure, the texts were transformed into a dense vector representation through the embedding layer, the CNN part identified important local features, and the BiGRU learned contextual and semantic connections. These two different features were combined in the “fusion” stage and divided into three classes using the final softmax classifier. Experimental results showed that the integrated CNN + BiGRU model provides higher accuracy and stability than separate CNNs or recurrent networks alone. The model efficiency is maintained, especially when working with small amounts of data. Future research plans to further improve this architecture by testing it on larger, more realistic-sized cases, as well as integrating it with attention mechanisms or transformer-based models.

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